

SCIENCE EUROPE

**PRACTICAL GUIDE TO
SUPPORTING DIVERSITY IN
RESEARCH ENVIRONMENTS**

with examples from Science Europe Member Organisations

February 2024

Colophon

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‘Practical Guide to Supporting Diversity in Research Environments’

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Foreword

The quality and impact of research depends on the inclusion and involvement of a diverse representation of the brightest minds and will be enhanced by the talent and resources of scientists from underrepresented groups.

Science Europe Members, research funding and performing organisations, understand the importance of equality, diversity, and inclusion across the processes that they implement, and recognise the role and responsibility that research organisations have in ensuring fair and inclusive national research systems across Europe.

Research organisations dedicate significant time and effort towards combatting bias, discrimination, and unfair treatment, and actions require continual review and update. Much attention has been directed towards gender equality in the last decade, yet much more work is needed. At the same time, there is an increase in the elements of diversity that require action and support, and diversity must now be recognised as a multi-faceted issue that includes factors such as disabilities, social background, and ethnicity. Actions to address this broader understanding of diversity requires long-term commitment from research organisations, the dedication of resources, and the acknowledgement that support for equality, diversity, and inclusion is both a moral and ethical imperative and a means of supporting research quality.

At a time when a number of major European policy initiatives are driving national and international research cultures in positive directions (see the [Diamond Open Access Initiative](#), a new [European Framework for Research Careers](#), and the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment](#) (CoARA), as examples), it is vital that equality, diversity, and inclusion is considered a core,

cross-cutting topic where advances, complementary to other initiatives, can and must continue to be made. Advances in our collective support for diversity in research systems contributes to 1) more attractive career prospects for talented individuals regardless of their gender, background, ethnicity, religion, and so on, 2) the evolution of research cultures towards more positive, supportive, and productive environments, and 3) the further embedding of our shared core values in institutional policies. This will ultimately improve the quality of research while fostering more attractive and fair research environments.

Science Europe calls on research organisations to bolster and expand on the actions they undertake to support equality, diversity, and inclusion, and to be bold and strive to lead by example when developing new policies and practices. This Practical Guide provides a first-of-a-kind insight into approaches to diversity by research organisations internationally. It aims to motivate and inspire research funding and performing organisations to appraise and adapt their institutional policies in support of greater diversity in human resources across our research environments.

Marc Schiltz

President of Science Europe 2017–2023

Science Europe Background

In 2021, Science Europe launched its [Strategy Plan for the period 2021–2026](#). This strategy included a priority focus on research culture. In a two-year exercise, a set of core values, integral to all aspects of research systems were discussed and agreed by the entire Science Europe Membership. The six shared values included ‘Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion’, placing it at the centre of discussions on the evolution of research cultures in Europe, both nationally and internationally.

In 2017, Science Europe published a [Practical Guide to Improving Gender Equality in Research Organisations](#).¹ Improving and supporting gender equality has been and continues to be a priority in R&I systems in Europe (see the European Commission’s [Gender Equality Strategy](#) as an example) and globally (the [Global Research Council Survey on Gender-Disaggregated Data](#)). As important advances are made, and our knowledge of the gender dimension in R&I systems deepens, so does our understanding of other elements of potential bias and discrimination, and the interplay between them.

1 The term ‘research organisations’ is used to refer to both research funding and research performing organisations.

Context and Focus

In this new Practical Guide, Science Europe explores what diversity means to research organisations, what actions are currently being taken to support this broadened understanding, and which challenges and barriers research funding and performing organisations currently face.

This guide considers diversity primarily from a human resources perspective and relates to individuals within our research environments. It is important to recognise that diversity should also be considered and supported in terms of research activities, contributions, outputs, and ideas. These elements of diversity also contribute to positive, effective, and inclusive research cultures, and other actions are dedicated to this aspect of diversity, such as through [the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#).

Science Europe is committed to supporting diversity in research in its broadest sense, both in terms of human resources and that of approaches to research studies. This guide contributes to that commitment with a focus on the people that make up our research systems. The guide focusses on ‘diversity’ as a prerequisite for being inclusive, and as a step in the process towards equality.

The Practical Guide presents both insights and recommendations based on the outcomes of a membership survey conducted in 2023 by Science Europe. This was done under the guidance of the Task Force on Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion (see Annex 1 for a list of members) as part of our wider strategic priority on ‘research culture’, led by the Working Group on Research Culture. Details about this survey and the responses collected are provided in Annex 2, and key results of the survey are presented throughout the guide, and more comprehensively in Annex 3. The recommendations are made to inspire practical actions that research funding and performing organisations can take to support diversity, both in their national systems, as well as internationally. A set of existing good practice examples are presented to guide the implementation of the recommendations made.

The Meaning of Diversity to Research Organisations

Our understanding and recognition of diversity continues to change as new forms of bias and discrimination are discovered in practices and processes. Research organisations invest significant time, effort, and resources into combatting bias, discrimination, and unfair treatment ([Science Europe, 2020](#)).

As part of this continual process, new action areas within the concept of diversity are identified. As such, definitions of diversity are not static and may be modified according to a variety of factors, including country and research domain and new research outputs. This chapter explores the breadth of the meaning of diversity for research organisations and provides recommendations on transparency, prioritisation, and monitoring.

Insight

Which elements of diversity are considered in any of the activities your organisation conducts towards the research community?

Gender remains the element of diversity most widely considered by research organisations. It is an area where significant action has been taken in recent years, but where it is recognised that more action is still needed. To this extent, the 2017 [Science Europe Practical Guide to Improving Gender Equality in Research Organisations](#) remains an important reference document, and the good practices and guidance described are highly complementary to those in this new guide.

Recommendations

- Research organisations should **develop strategies** for identifying priority action areas based on their own specific contexts and should involve other relevant stakeholder groups in the process.
- Research organisations should **be fully transparent and openly communicate** about the elements of diversity that they consider in their policies and practices.
 - ↳ Research organisations should set up internal processes through which they can proactively identify and act upon elements of diversity not previously considered in policies or practices, but which may be a source of unfair treatment, bias, or discrimination.
 - ↳ Research organisations should be clear on elements of diversity that they are unable to consider, and the reasons why (lack of available data, for instance).
 - ↳ Where different definitions of diversity are considered at domain, field, or programme specific levels, this should be clearly stated.
- Research organisations should continually **monitor their processes** for any forms of potential bias and update their actionable diversity elements whenever needed.
- Research organisations should proactively **share data, evidence, and learnings** with other organisations so that those without the necessary resources can benefit. A lack of data on certain diversity elements should not limit actions where data from other organisations or systems is available.

Collecting and Using Data on Diversity Elements

The basis of our understanding on the state of the art of equality, diversity, and inclusion within research systems is data: it is important for strategy setting, action prioritisation, as well as monitoring and evaluation.

Data can be collected at numerous levels and as part of a range of processes. In some cases, insights from datasets are applicable across a wide array of policy settings. In other cases, specific data are needed to understand and develop actions for certain contexts. It must also be noted that data on diversity elements are often highly sensitive and personal. Therefore, discussions on the collection and use of such data must be accompanied by discussions around data protection and safeguarding. Further, data collection should always be linked to clear and specific objectives, and it should be noted that data disclosure is an individual's choice.

This chapter explores the extent to which data are collected at organisational and country levels and provides recommendations on expanding data collection and evidence sharing.

Insight

Does your organisation use any **country-level data** related to diversity?

■ Yes ■ No ■ I do not know

N = 28

Does your organisation collect data related to diversity as part of its processes and practices?

89% of responding organisations collect disaggregated data on all applications received.

93% of responding organisations collect disaggregated data from successful applications.

86% of responding organisations collect disaggregated data on representatives in decision-making bodies.

Recommendations

- Data related to diversity elements are often highly sensitive and personal. Research organisations should **only collect such data where it is important** to support research quality and equality, diversity, and inclusion.
 - ↳ Where such data can be collected, the highest standards of safeguarding and data protection should be used.
- Where data are currently not able to be collected, but would be of use to research organisations in their support for diversity and quality, research organisations should **advocate to their competent authorities** for exceptional allowances to collect sensitive data, with appropriate safeguards, to support their activities.
 - ↳ The open publication of evidence and reports, and participation in international expert groups are examples of means of fostering this form of mutual learning.
- Research organisations should **complement and contextualise** any diversity-related data that they collect with data that may be available at a national (and international) level.

- ↳ Research organisations are encouraged to collaborate with relevant competent authorities to maximise the use of available data to support evidence-based actions.
- Where research organisations collect diversity data on applicants, panels, or decision-making bodies, such data should be broken down (where possible) into sub-categories (by field of research, funding programme, or academic position, as examples) to allow for **deeper analysis**.
 - ↳ Many sources of bias are specific to processes (for example, external peer review) or to career stage (they may specifically impact early-career researchers).
- Supporting diversity is a **moral and ethical imperative**. Research organisations should not consider a lack of own data as a barrier to action; they should use available data and evidence from other sources, and should seek support and collaboration with other research organisations, nationally and internationally.
 - ↳ Taking action may contribute to the provision of data that can then be used to further adapt and improve the support provided.

Positive Action Measures

Positive actions can be defined as measures that 1) target protected groups to enable or encourage members of those groups to overcome or minimise disadvantage, 2) meet the different needs of the protected group, or 3) enable or encourage persons in protected groups to participate in an activity'.² Support for diversity requires continual and deliberate action and engagement. Public research organisations may consider their support for diversity in terms of both quality and impact, and as a moral and ethical imperative. In these ways, many research organisations implement positive action measures. See also Chapter 8 of this guide.

Insight

Does your organisation implement any 'positive action' measures to support diversity?

Recommendations

- Research organisations should **clearly define the intended effects** of their positive action measures in support of diversity.
- Research organisations should **consider the breadth and extent to which they implement positive action measures** and expand those actions to further elements of diversity where appropriate.
- Positive action measures should be **monitored and evaluated**. The evidence gathered from these exercises should be shared with other research organisations to promote mutual learning.
 - ➔ Again, the open publication of evidence and reports, and participation in international expert groups is a key means of fostering this form of mutual learning.

2 See the [UK Equality Act 2010](#) as an example

The Challenges to Overcome

Research funding and performing organisations occupy an important position in their respective national and international research systems and the policies and practices that they implement have significant influence over the research that is conducted. Changes to policies and practices must be made with care and attention.

This chapter explores some of the common challenges faced by research organisations in their activities to support diversity and provides recommendations for joint actions, evidence gathering, and context specificities.

Insight

Asked to share the biggest or most urgent challenges facing responding organisations in their support of diversity, 28 respondents shared 60 examples. Common challenges shared by at least three respondents:

Recommendations

- Research organisations should **advocate dedicated budgets and support** for their activities to implement diversity-related policies and practices.
- Research funding organisations and research performing organisations within national systems should actively **discuss, collaborate, and develop joint actions** to support diversity.
- Research organisations should **pilot, monitor, and evaluate** their policies and practices, and share the information they gather with the research community to build an evidence base to support effective policy and practice changes.
 - ↳ Research funding organisations may consider funding ‘research on research’ in the area of support actions for diversity.
 - ↳ Research performing organisations may consider running or commissioning evaluations of processes where support for diversity could have the most impact.
 - ↳ Links to other policy initiatives, such as research career observatories and reform of research assessment studies, may help to collect complementary evidence.
 - ↳ Global data outcomes should be gathered and promoted, in collaboration with supra-national bodies (such as UNESCO).
- Research organisations should consider **support measures for diversity in a field-specific manner**, whenever relevant, and engage with field experts to develop appropriate actions.
 - ↳ Effective measures to combat bias, discrimination, bullying, or harassment will likely vary between research areas that require fieldwork compared to those that are desk-based, or between highly collaborative fields and those more based on individual activities.
 - ↳ Evidence-gathering exercises should support the identification of field-specific diversity issues on which action should be taken.
- Research organisations that state ‘equality, diversity, and inclusion’ as part of their strategic activities, should make an **explicit link** to it as an element of research quality.
 - ↳ Such statements should be backed up by the provision of appropriate resources to enable effective actions.

Good practices by Science Europe Member Organisations

Research organisations continually monitor, evaluate, and adjust their policies and practices as the conduct and management of research evolves. Mutual learning and knowledge sharing between similar organisations at an international level are key parts of these adaptations and help improve research systems.

Research organisations rely on good practice examples from others, and contribute their own achievements and lessons learned. This chapter highlights some of the many best-practice examples collected through the Science Europe Survey on Diversity and during the drafting of this guide, and offers recommendations on how research organisations may consider similar actions.

Insight

Asked to share good practice examples of actions supporting diversity, 28 respondents shared 71 individual examples. Common good practices shared by at least five respondents:

Provides guidelines
and training

Establishes committees/working
groups to deal with diversity issues

Publishes
Gender/Diversity
Equality Plans

**Provides
dedicated funding**

Participates in research projects
(ie. GenderAction +)

**Implements
Narrative CVs**

Good Practices

The following examples provide a snapshot of some of the many good practices that exist. This is not an exhaustive list, but showcases examples from a range of organisations.

The **French National Research Agency** (ANR) is committed to contributing to the development of a policy aimed at reducing inequalities between women and men in higher education and research. As an example of this commitment, the agency published a [guide on the use of inclusive communication and the avoidance of gender stereotyping](#).

Research organisations should consider using inclusive language in all their communications (both external and internal) to avoid promoting stereotypes and stereotyping.

The **German Research Foundation** (DFG) 'Research-Oriented Equity and Diversity Standards' define standards for sustainable gender equality and the promotion of diversity across the research landscape.

The **Executive Agency for Higher Education, research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania** (UEFISCDI) was the first public institution in Romania to undertake the elaboration and implementation of a [Gender Equality Plan](#), strengthening the organisation's position as an innovator and as a national leader on issues of gender equality.

Research organisations occupy an important position within national research systems and have specific responsibilities for supporting diversity to enhance their respective research systems to the extent possible. Leading by example can help to promote system-level change by guiding organisations and individuals.

The **Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)** has implemented policies and programme-specific action points within the framework of its [action plan on gender, equality, diversity, and inclusion](#) to promote a fair, transparent, and accessible research environment. Direct dialogue to national research performing institutions is crucial part of this plan and is important for a good collaboration between all actors of the research community and to further promote equality, diversity and inclusion broadly.

Research organisations should proactively establish dialogue and collaboration with their respective research communities on actions to support diversity.

The **Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)** publishes a series of [short, good practice manuals](#) on topics such as inclusive research conferences, inclusive dissemination, and non-biased evaluation.

The **Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life, and Welfare (FORTE)** offers clear [guidance and training for panel members](#) on issues of gender equality, including being transparent on

potential pitfalls of a gender equal review process and how to work practically to avoid them.

Actions to support diversity are often context specific. Research organisations should provide guidance and training specific to processes that are critical in supporting diversity such as bias training in panel evaluations as an example.

The **Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)** offers [flexibility in seniority limits and fellowship extension possibilities](#) in case of pregnancy, maternity leave, parental leave, military service, or long-term sickness.

Science Foundation Ireland (SFI) include 'Personal Support', 'Childcare and companion travel', and 'Assistive Technology' as eligible costs in the [SFI Grant Budget Policy](#). Grant holders are permitted to use the flexibility afforded in the Grant conditions to contribute to the salary of a support person to assist the grant holder or a team member in day-to-day tasks necessary to successfully carry out the research programme.

Built-in flexibility in policies and practices can be a simple yet powerful tool to support diversity. Research organisations should consider how flexibility clauses in their policies can alleviate potential sources of bias or discrimination.

Fundação
para a Ciência
e a Tecnologia

The **Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)** has created the [RESTART programme](#) as a new funding instrument to promote equal opportunities for researchers who have taken parental leave. It was established as parental leave was identified as a common barrier to career progression.

**Swiss National
Science Foundation**

The **Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)** integrates gender equality measures directly into its funding programmes. [PRIMA grants](#) are aimed at excellent women researchers who show a high potential for obtaining a professorship.

Where specific challenges or needs are identified, dedicated funding instruments (for RFOs) or career progression programmes (for RPOs) should be considered as a positive action measure.

**Swiss National
Science Foundation**

The **Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)** Training on Evaluation Practices (STEP) implements a three-step approach to train reviewers and raise awareness about biases. The project comprises three measures to convey information about the SNSF evaluation standards: 1) documentation on the grant platforms, 2) funding-instrument specific training, and 3) an e-learning platform. The platform was launched in August 2023 for testing and feedback. The first module in this e-learning platform provides information on best practices for the scientific evaluation of research proposals, in particular highlighting the influence of various types of biases on project evaluation.

Training is an essential component of the support for diversity that research organisations can provide. Research funding organisations should fund and provide training for all in the research system and research performing organisations should promote and incentivise training schemes.

UK Research and Innovation

UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) uses a number of strategic interventions to promote and foster a more inclusive R&I system, including through the use of narrative CVs and as part of its 2023 [Organisation-wide Strategy on Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion](#).

Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare

The **Italian National Institute for Nuclear Physics** (INFN) [recognises and implements](#) the good practice originating from the European Research Executive Agency where guidelines are provided on the calculation of research experience for postdoctoral fellowships under Horizon Europe including where, for instance, maternity leave is counted as 18 months per child.

Positive action measures to support work/life balance and personal/family considerations should be considered in policies and practices, where appropriate, and can have significant impact on fostering positive and inclusive research cultures.

CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTÍFICAS

The **Spanish National Research Council** (CSIC) distributed a survey in 2023 to assess the situation of disabled CSIC employees, the results of which will be made available and actioned upon.

The interconnected nature of diversity elements (referred to as intersectionality) is an important consideration for the overall support of diversity in research systems, and evidence should be gathered on these interconnections.

Many Science Europe Member Organisations actively participate in international projects that aim to advance equality, diversity, and inclusion across the European Research Area. GenderAction+ is one such example where numerous Science Europe members participate.

Beyond the activities conducted by research organisations targeting their own processes and national contexts, engagement in international initiatives is important way for research organisations to support systemic improvements for the benefit of all.

Swedish
Research
Council

The **Swedish Research Council** (VR) regularly conducts [gender equality observations](#) in review panels to identify room for improvement of routines, instructions, and other aspects of the review process to promote gender equality in the assessment of research applications.

Research organisations should have set periodic or continual procedures in place to monitor and review practices diversity support across all their processes, including, for instance, in the assessment of research applications.

Next Steps

Supporting Diversity is a continual process, requiring constant review and adjustment. This practical guide highlights numerous common challenges that require urgent action. It also emphasizes the multitude of good practices that already exist and demonstrates the shared commitment of research organisations in Europe to support diversity in their respective national systems, as well as internationally. Combatting bias/discrimination and working towards fairer research systems is a continual endeavour.

The Science Europe Survey on Diversity collected information on the plans of responding organisations for initiatives and actions relating to equality, diversity, and inclusion. Nearly 80% of responding organisations provided activities and actions that will be undertaken in the coming years.

Does your organisation have plans for any new initiatives or activities of relevance to the subject of Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion in the coming years?

Establish new or updated Equality plans
Develop (further) guidance and recommendations

Participate in national initiatives
Implement (further) positive action measures

Undertake/commission studies

Take action to improve research culture

This survey result demonstrates a clear and continued commitment to supporting diversity from research organisations across Europe. For its part, Science Europe commits to continuing its work on what is now a long-established priority area, supporting its members and the broader research community in planned and possible future actions. As part of this activity, a multitude of good practice examples have been collected, with many more still to come. Science Europe will continue to collect and share these with

the research community through a living collection on the Science Europe website, and will use these, along with the challenges described, as a basis for future activities.

Equality, diversity, and inclusion are core values in our respective national and shared international research systems. Supporting diversity, as addressed in this guide, is a prerequisite to inclusive conditions and activities, that in turn can lead to more equal research systems and thus better research results. The recommendations in this guide offer insights and possible directions for research organisations. The guide also highlights the existing commitment of research organisations to fostering improvements to research environments as a moral and ethical imperative and also as a means of supporting research quality. Ongoing actions on diversity complement and bolster other policy activities such as actions on careers in research, open science, and the reform of research assessment. Collectively, the aim of these initiatives is to build positive and healthy research cultures that support research quality and impact, by attracting talented individuals. It is through the lens of research culture, that 'EDI' is now being extended to 'EDIB', where a sense of 'belonging' is also featured as a key attribute of positive and healthy research cultures.

Annex 1 - Contributors

The report was written and edited by the Science Europe Office, supported by the Science Europe Task Force on Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion. The Science Europe Working Group on Research Culture and the Science Europe Governing Board were consulted on an advanced draft.

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Annex 2 - Survey

Science Europe Survey on Diversity

Method

In April 2023, all Science Europe Member Organisations (including both research funding and performing organisations) were invited to participate in a survey developed by the Task Force on Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion. By the deadline in July 2023, a total of 28 out of 40 Member Organisations (70%) had responded. The response rate was balanced: 1) between research funding and research performing members of Science Europe; 2) across the geographical coverage of the Science Europe membership; and 3) between small, medium, and large members. The results were analysed and discussed by the Task Force and, where needed, respondents were contacted for additional information.

Survey Data

Respondents answered the survey with confidentiality to Science Europe. Due to the nature of the survey and the responses provided, the data cannot be anonymised.

Survey Structure

General Information

*** In which capacity are you responding to this survey?**

- As a research funding organisation (RFO)
- As a research performing organisation (RPO)
- As both a research funding and a research performing organisation (RFO+RPO)

Organisation-level positions on Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion

* Which elements of diversity are considered in any of the activities your organisation conducts towards the research community (assessment processes, monitoring, data collection, and so on)?

- Gender
- Sex (as biologically determined, if differentiated from gender)
- Gender expression (individual expression)
- Ethnicity
- Disability
- Age
- Seniority
- Affiliation
- Geographic representation
- Socio-economic background
- Cultural background
- Sexual orientation
- Religion
- We do not consider any elements of diversity
- Other: _____

Comments (optional): _____

* Does your organisation mention Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion (or its constituent elements) in its statutes, strategy plan, or other organisation-wide policies and guidelines?

- Yes
- No

Comments (optional): _____

* Does your organisation have a specific role, team, or department dedicated to Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion activities?

- Yes
- No

* Please provide additional information and/or links to any relevant documents

Comments (optional): _____

* Does your organisation monitor/evaluate any elements of Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion in relation to its overall organisational performance?

- Yes
- No

* Please provide additional information and/or links to any relevant documents

Since what year have these monitoring/evaluation exercises taken place?

Comments (optional): _____

* Does your organisation publicly report on any of the previously identified elements of diversity as part of annual or general reporting?

- Yes
- No

*** Which of the previously identified elements of diversity does your organisation include in its reporting?**

- Gender
- Sex (as biologically determined, if differentiated from gender)
- Gender expression (individual expression)
- Ethnicity
- Disability
- Age
- Seniority
- Affiliation
- Geographic representation
- Socio-economic background
- Cultural background
- Sexual orientation
- Religion
- Other: _____

*** Please provide additional information and/or links to any relevant documents**

Comments (optional): _____

*** Does your organisation implement any ‘positive action’ measures to support diversity?**

- Yes
- No

Positive action, for the purposes of this survey is defined as any “measures that are targeted at under-represented groups in order to enable or encourage members of those groups to overcome or minimise disadvantage.”

*** Please provide additional information and/or links to any relevant documents**

Comments (optional): _____

Data Collection Related to Diversity

* Does your organisation use any country-level data related to diversity?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

* Is any country-level data (national statistic, published studies, and so on) available on the percentage share of the researcher pool according to the following elements?

	Yes	No	Do not know
Gender	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sex (if differentiated from gender, biologically determined)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Gender expression (individual expression)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Ethnicity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Disability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Age	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Seniority	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Affiliation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Geographic representation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Socio-economic background	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cultural background	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sexual orientation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Religion	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

- * Are these data focused on any specific sub-groups of researchers (early-career researchers, professors, and so on)?

How are these data collected (national census, research studies, and so on)?

- * Does your organisation use this country-level data for diversity analysis?

- * Are there any national legal frameworks in place for the collection of diversity-related data?

- Yes, these have been in place for 5 years or more
- Yes, this is a recent development (less than 5 years)
- No

Please provide additional information and/or links to any relevant documents

Is there a specific committee, office, or role that implements and oversees these national legal frameworks (for example, ombuds office, national committee or commissioner for equality)?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

- * If yes, please specify:

Data Collection in Applications for Funding (RFOs) and Recruitment/Promotion (RPOs)

* Does your organisation collect disaggregated data on the number of applications received according to specific diversity considerations?

- Yes
- No
- Other: _____

* On which of the following categories related to diversity does your organisation collect disaggregated data?

- Gender
- Sex (if differentiated from gender, as biologically determined)
- Gender expression (individual expression)
- Ethnicity
- Disability
- Age
- Seniority
- Affiliation
- Geographic representation
- Socio-economic background
- Cultural background
- Sexual orientation
- Religion
- Other: _____

Since what year has this data collection taken place?

* Does your organisation collect disaggregated data on the number of successful applications according to specific diversity considerations?

- Yes
- No
- Other: _____

*** On which of the following categories related to diversity does your organisation collect disaggregated data for successful applications?**

- Gender
- Sex (if differentiated from gender, as biologically determined)
- Gender expression (individual expression)
- Ethnicity
- Disability
- Age
- Seniority
- Affiliation
- Geographic representation
- Socio-economic background
- Cultural background
- Sexual orientation
- Religion
- Other: _____

Since what year has this data collection taken place?

Data collection related to assessment/decision-making bodies

*** Does your organisation collect disaggregated data on the number of representatives in decision-making bodies according to specific Diversity considerations?**

- Yes
- No

In a research funding capacity, think of, for example, assessment panels.

In a research performing capacity, think of, for example, recruitment and promotion boards.

*** For which of the following categories related to diversity does your organisation collect disaggregated data on the number of representatives in decision-making bodies?**

- Gender
- Sex (if differentiated from gender, as biologically determined)
- Gender expression (individual expression)
- Ethnicity
- Disability
- Age
- Seniority
- Affiliation
- Geographic representation
- Socio-economic background
- Cultural background
- Sexual orientation
- Religion
- Other: _____

*** Please provide additional information and/or links to any relevant documents:**

Since what year has this data collection taken place?

*** Does your organisation have any specific policies and/or practices relating to the diversity of representatives in assessment/decision-making bodies?**

- Yes
- No

*** Please provide additional information and/or links to any relevant documents:**

Since what year has this data collection taken place?

Comments (optional): _____

Current State of Affairs

In relation to any of the aspects touched-upon in this survey, or in relation to Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion more broadly, please share up to three relevant good practice examples from your organisation or national-system.

Example 1: _____

Example 2: _____

Example 3: _____

These good practices could be policy actions, initiatives, reports, workshops, or committees, for instance.

In your view, what are the biggest or most urgent challenges facing your organisation in supporting diversity in the research system your organisation operates within?

Challenge 1: _____

Challenge 2: _____

Challenge 3: _____

Which other types of diversity, besides those listed in the survey, does your organisation consider in its policies and practices?

- Disciplinary contexts (diversity of fields of knowledge)
- Types of research (applied research, fundamental research, mission-oriented, and so on)
- Research funds (funding mechanisms - projects, grants, institutions; short vs long term funding; strategic goal vs open goals; articulation with other sectors - industrial, cultural, social, and so on)
- Research approaches (sustainability science, citizen science, and so on)
- Research assessment groups (criteria, panels, peer review pools, and so on)
- Research outputs
- Research institutions
- Researchers' roles and research team profiles
- Researchers' skills and competencies
- Researchers' career pathways
- Externalities (social, economic, education, innovation): contributions that researchers and research make for the benefit of society
- Research culture values (diverse practices that contribute to robustness, openness, transparency, and the inclusiveness of research and research process)
- I do not know
- Other: _____

Future Perspectives and Remaining Challenges

*** Does your organisation have plans for any new initiatives or activities of relevance to the subject of Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion in the coming years?**

- Yes
- No

*** Please provide additional information and/or links to any relevant documents:**

Comments (optional): _____

*** Please describe what you think the role of Science Europe should be in relation to supporting Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion in research systems**

Is there any additional information that you would like to provide as part of this survey?

Annex 3 – Survey Results

In which capacity of your organisation are you responding to this survey?

- As a research funding organisation (RFO)
- As a research performing organisation (RPO)
- As both a research funding and a research performing organisation (RFO+RPO) N = 28

Which elements of diversity are considered in any of the activities your organisation conducts towards the research community?

Does your organisation mention Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion (or its constituent elements) in its statutes, strategy plan, or other organisation-wide policies and guidelines?

■ Yes (%)

N = 28

Does your organisation have a specific role, team, or department dedicated to Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion activities?

■ % Yes ■ % No

N = 28

Does your organisation publicly report on any of the previously identified elements of diversity as part of annual or general reporting?

■ % Yes ■ % No

N = 28

Which of the previously identified elements of diversity does your organisation include in its reporting?

N = 28

Does your organisation mandate a Gender Equality Plan (GEP) and/or other diversity-related plans as part of your funding/grant agreements?

N = 28

Does your organisation implement any 'positive action' measures to support diversity?

■ % Yes ■ % No

N = 28

Does your organisation use any country-level data related to diversity?

■ Yes ■ No ■ I do not know

N = 28

Is any country-level data (national statistic, published studies, and so on) available on the percentage share of the researcher pool according to the following elements?

N = 19

Are there any national legal frameworks in place for the collection of diversity-related data?

54%

of responding organisations operate in national systems where legal frameworks have been in place for **more than five** years.

14%

operate in national systems where frameworks have been in place for **less than five** years.

32%

of responding organisations operate in national systems where **no legal frameworks** are in place.

Does your organisation collect disaggregated data on the number of applications received according to specific diversity considerations?

■ % Yes ■ % No

N = 28

Does your organisation collect disaggregated data on successful applications according to specific diversity considerations?

■ % Yes ■ % No

N = 28

When operating in a research funding capacity, are the data collected broken down into further categories?

45% of responding organisations say the data collected are broken down by funding scheme and research field.

When operating in a research performing capacity, are the data collected broken down into further categories?

Responding organisations who say the data collected are broken down by position and research field: **25%**

Does your organisation have plans for any new initiatives or activities of relevance to the subject of Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion in the coming years?

79%

of responding organisations have plans for new activities related to equality, diversity, and inclusion in the coming years.

Supplementary Question - Which other types of diversity, besides those listed in the survey, does your organisation consider in its policies and practices?

<u>Disciplinary contexts (<i>diversity of fields of knowledge</i>)</u>	79%
<u>Research assessment groups (<i>criteria, panels, peer review pools...</i>)</u>	68%
<u>Research funds (<i>funding mechanisms – projects, grants, institutions; short- vs long-term funding; strategic vs open goals; articulation with other sectors – industrial, cultural, social...</i>)</u>	68%
<u>Types of research (<i>applied, fundamental, mission-oriented...</i>)</u>	68%
<u>Researchers' career pathways</u>	61%
<u>Research outputs</u>	50%
<u>Research institutions</u>	50%
<u>Research culture values (<i>diverse practices that contribute to robustness, openness, transparency, and inclusiveness of the research (process)</i>)</u>	50%
<u>Researchers' skills and competencies</u>	46%
<u>Externalities (social, economic, education, innovation): contributions that researchers and research make for the benefit of society</u>	43%
<u>Research approaches (<i>sustainability science, citizen science...</i>)</u>	39%

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